

POSSIBLE ANTIAMOEBCIC AGENTS. MANNICH BASES FROM
8-HYDROXYQUINOLINES

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Several Mannich bases have been prepared from 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid, with a view to testing their antiamoebic activity.

Substituted 8-hydroxyquinolines, viz., di-iodoquin, vioform and chiniofon, are important amoebicidal drugs. Burckhalter and Edgerton (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4837), Edgerton and Burckhalter (*ibid.*, 1952, 74, 5209) and Burckhalter *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1954, 76, 4902) have observed interesting amoebicidal activity in a group of compounds obtained by substituting dialkylaminoalkyl groupings by the Mannich reaction for the iodine atom in vioform. This prompted the authors to make a similar replacement of the iodine atom in chiniofon by dialkylaminoalkyl groupings and to study the antiamoebic activity of the resulting compounds (III).

The Mannich reaction with hydroxyquinolines has not been extensively studied; a few reactions of 8-hydroxyquinoline with dimethylamine, morpholine, piperidine and formaldehyde are described in the literature (Ger. Pat. 92309; *Frdl.*, 1899, 4, 103) and that 4-hydroxyquinolines have been submitted to the Mannich reaction by Price and Jackson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1282). The present work was therefore undertaken to study this reaction in greater details with 8-hydroxyquinoline 5-sulphonic acid (I).

(I)

(II)

(III)

8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (I), required for the work, was obtained by the method of Matsumura (*ibid.*, 1927, 49, 810). For the preparation of the Mannich bases the sodium salt of compound (I), different secondary amines and formaldehyde were employed, adopting the same procedure described earlier (Ger. Pat. 92309; *Frdl.*, *loc. cit.*). It was, however, observed that only in the case of piperidine, the Mannich base could be separated successfully from the starting material, but with other secondary amines the expected Mannich bases could not be isolated in the pure form.

The Mannich reaction with the free sulphonic acid (I) instead of its sodium salt was also carried out, and it was found that the amine salts (II) of the expected Mannich bases (III) were produced. The lower secondary amines, viz., dimethylamine, diethylamine, di-*n*-propylamine and diethanolamine, however, did not furnish the amine salts, but yielded the Mannich bases directly. This may be ascribed to the instability of the

lower amine salts. The isolation of the free Mannich bases from their amine salts was achieved by acidifying the hot alcoholic solution of the salts with acetic acid and cooling the mixture.

EXPERIMENTAL

8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic Acid (I) and its Sodium Salt.—(I) was prepared according to the method of Matsumara (*loc. cit.*). From 14½ g. of 8-hydroxyquinoline only 20 g. of the sulphonated product (I), m.p. 310°, could be obtained, yield 80% (reported 96%). The sodium salt was prepared by suspending the sulphonic acid in hot water and neutralising with sodium carbonate. On cooling, the sodium salt crystallised out.

Sodium Salt of 7-sec.-Aminomethyl-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic Acid.—A mixture of the sodium salt (2.47 g., 0.01M), paraformaldehyde (0.3 g., 0.01M) and the secondary amine (0.1M) in 150 c.c. of alcohol was refluxed for 6 hours on a water-bath. The mixture was then concentrated under reduced pressure and the yellow solid obtained was washed with alcohol and finally crystallised from *n*-butanol-ether mixture (1:5). The m. p., yields and % sulphur of the compounds are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No	X=	M. P.	Yield.	Mol. formula.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.
1	Piperidino-	281°	75%	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₂ SNa	8.90	9.30
2	Morpholino-	284°	80	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₂ SNa	10.32	9.75
3	Diethylamino-	286°	85	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₂ SNa	10.64	9.64°

sec.-Amine Salts of 7-sec.-Aminomethyl-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic Acid.—A mixture of 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (I) (2.25 g., 0.01M), paraformaldehyde (0.3 g., 0.01M) and 0.1M in the above case of piperidine and morpholine and 0.05M with di-*n* butylamine and di-*isobutylamine*, in 30-50 c.c. alcohol, was heated under reflux over a water-bath for 6 hours. The mixture was then concentrated under reduced pressure and the residue washed with ether. The solid, thus obtained, was crystallised from acetone-alcohol mixture (1:1). The m. p., yield and % sulphur of the compounds obtained are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

TABLE II (contd.)

No.	X =	M. P.	Yield.	Mol. formula.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.
1	Di- <i>n</i> -butylamino-	182-83°	50%	C ₂₈ H ₄₈ O ₄ N ₂ S	6.34	6.46
2	Di- <i>isobutyl</i> amino-	151-52°	60	C ₂₆ H ₄₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	6.21	6.46
3	Piperidino-	194-95°	80	C ₂₉ H ₃₉ O ₄ N ₂ S	7.90	7.86
4	Morpholino-	184-85°	85	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₂ S	7.75	7.79

The isolation of the free sulphonic acids from the above amine salts was achieved by acidifying the hot alcoholic solution of the salts (1 g. of the salt in 10 c.c. of alcohol) with acetic acid and cooling the mixture. The crystals which separated out were filtered and washed with boiling alcohol. Their m.p., yields (based on their conversion from the amine salts) and their analysis (% sulphur) are recorded in Table III (compounds 5-8).

TABLE III

No.	X =	M. P.	Yield.	Mol. formula.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.
1	Dimethylamino-	198-200°	71%	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂ S	11.12	11.35
2	Diethylamino-	223-24°	66	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₂ S	10.23	10.32
3	Di- <i>n</i> -propylamino-	166-67°	65	C ₁₆ H ₂₉ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.13	9.47
4	Di-ethanolamino-	177-78°	60	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₆ N ₂ S	9.15	9.35
5	Di- <i>n</i> -butylamino-	206-208°	75	C ₁₆ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	8.61	8.74
6	Di- <i>isobutyl</i> amino-	199-200°	70	C ₁₆ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	8.62	8.74
7	Piperidino-	211°	80	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.81	9.93
8	Morpholino-	213-14°	85	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₂ S	9.62	9.87

7-sec.-Aminomethyl-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic Acid.—By following the above procedure with 2.25 g. (0.01 M) of 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid, 0.3 g. (0.01 M) of paraformaldehyde and 0.1 M of the secondary amines (dimethylamine, diethylamine, di-*n*-propylamine and diethanolamine) the free Mannich bases were obtained. Their m.p., yields and analysis (% sulphur) are shown in Table III (compounds 1-4).

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